

Extracting, Annotating, and Publishing Icelandic Style-Shift Data

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Abstract

We describe the methods that we use as part of the ERC project Explaining Individual Lifespan Change in order to extract data from the Icelandic Parliament Corpus, manually annotate the extracted data for the purpose of analyzing sociolinguistic variables, and eventually publish the annotated database in open access under a Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) and using a well established repository that is suitable for the digital humanities (CLARIN). We furthermore discuss how the data that we extract from the parliament corpus gains more qualitative depth by us interviewing some of the politicians in question directly.

Keywords

sociolinguistics, style-shift, parliament data, annotation, database publication

1. Introduction

Our project, Explaining Individual Lifespan Change (EILisCh), was recently awarded an ERC Starting Grant to study sociolinguistic lifespan change in the Icelandic Parliament Corpus, which is a part of the Icelandic Gigaword Corpus (Steingrímsson et al. 2018; Steingrímsson, Barkarson, and Örnólfsson 2020). In this paper, we describe how we make use of this big data humanities resource to extract the data that we need, manually annotate the sociolinguistic variables that we are interested in and publish the data in open access in a suitable repository. We also describe how we use direct interviews with our subjects to gain more qualitative depth and how these, as well, will be made publicly available in order to facilitate future research.

Sociolinguistic research focuses on sociolinguistic variables, i.e., cases of linguistic usage where there are two or more ways of saying the same thing. The English examples in (1) show the case of Negative Concord (Labov 1972; Blanchette 2013).

- (1) a. We don't need no education. (Negative Concord)
b. We don't need any education. (Prescriptively Standard English)

In a variety of English where Negative Concord is variably used along with Prescriptively

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Standard English, as in the *any* example, the two examples mean the same thing and the same speaker can alternate between the two forms. This brings us to the concept of style-shift which is the fact that it depends on contextual factors, i.e., how formal the setting is, to what extent the two variants are used.

The study of lifespan change adds another layer to this empirical picture by studying how sociolinguistic variables evolve in their use over the course of someone’s life. For example, speakers may express a different level of overall formal speech at different stages in their lives (Stefánsdóttir and Ingason 2018; Grama et al. 2023) or they may change to what extent they style shift at all, modifying their stylistic range over time (MacKenzie, forthcoming).

Our project contributes to the study of lifespan change in a few different ways. It is a high-definition study (Stefánsdóttir and Ingason 2018) in the sense that we study speakers on a continuous time axis. In a field that focuses overwhelmingly on English, it adds empirical facts from Icelandic, an important act of inclusion. Furthermore, the study makes use of the fact that Iceland is a small community with good access to local politicians by interviewing some of the politicians directly for qualitative depth. All of the data in question will be made publicly available for future use by the research community.

2. Extracting style-shift from the Icelandic parliament corpus

We examine a variable in Icelandic that is called Stylistic Fronting (SF) (Maling 1980; Thráinsson 2007; Holmberg 2006). SF is an optional movement of an element into a phonological subject gap, such as shown in (2), where *lesnar* has been fronted. For comparison, (3) shows a parallel example with SF.

- (2) Bækur [_{CP} sem lesnar eru til skemmtunar] eru bestar.
 books [_{CP} that read are for entertainment] are best
 ‘Books that are read for entertainment are the best ones.’
- (3) Bækur [_{CP} sem eru lesnar til skemmtunar] eru bestar.
 books [_{CP} that are read for entertainment] are best
 ‘Books that are read for entertainment are the best ones.’

We developed a Python script that goes through the parliament section of the Icelandic gigaword corpus and extracts all examples of the type shown above. The more abstract patterns that we match in the corpus, using the PoS-tags provided with the corpus, are as follows:

- (4) relative complementizer (sem) – non-finite main verb – finite auxiliary
 (5) relative complementizer (sem) – finite auxiliary – non-finite main verb

We furthermore take advantage of the metadata provided with the corpus and output a tsv (tab separated values) file where each example of potential SF is accompanied by information about the name of the relevant Member of Parliament, their gender, date of birth, date of the speech, party affiliation, whether they were in the majority or the minority, as well as the full text of the sentence in question and a link to the parliament website where audio and video can often be accessed. We also include frequency information about the main verb, so that potential lexical

frequency effects can also be tracked in subsequent analysis.

3. Annotating sociolinguistic variables

For selected MP's, we verify the automatic coding of SF by manually comparing the audio recordings and the transcript that is given in the corpus. This is only possible for the most recent years as the parliament does not have recordings for very old speeches. We have measured the accuracy of the transcription with respect to SF and found that although there are some differences, they do not change the overall picture of SF that is found by the automatic coding (Stefánsdóttir and Ingason 2024).

The automatic coding assigns the value 1 to examples with SF and 0 to examples that are potential environment for SF but where SF has not been applied. For the manual coding, the same values are used, 1 for SF and 0 for non-SF, and while there is usually agreement between the two codes, the automatic and the manual one, there exist cases where an automatic 1 becomes manual 0 and vice versa. The manual coding also includes a -1 code for examples where the audio recording does not contain an environment for SF (the example is outside the so-called envelope of variation).

We are currently working on manual coding of some of the most important MP's and their use of stylistic fronting, but the project will also soon include the same method for coding so-called hard speech, a dialect that is linked to the northern part of Iceland. We have two hypotheses regarding the variable: The First is that Members of Parliament who move to the capital in the south decrease their rate of hard speech as they settle in in the capital region to carry out their work in the parliament. Second, is that these Members of Parliament either stay stable or increase their use of hard speech, as an act of expressing their identity (Eckert 1989, 2001). For this part of the study, we will use a program that phonetically transcribes all the words from the speeches in both dialects and then our script will extract examples where there are differences between pronunciation in the south and in the north, which will eventually be listened to by our annotators.

4. Adding qualitative interviews

One of the features that make work in the humanities valuable is that it often emphasizes qualitative depth when research is carried out. We believe that it is important to not let go of the qualitative aspect of the humanities, even when quantitative big data methods also play a large role in the digital humanities. In the pilot study for the EILisCh project, Stefánsdóttir and Ingason (2018), we included a direct interview with the subject of the study, former finance minister of Iceland, Steingrímur J. Sigfússon. This greatly improved our opportunities to interpret the quantitative findings and gain a deeper understanding of the empirical picture.

Our project is currently adding interviews with more selected MP's and we believe this aspect of the study makes a good argument for carrying out this kind of work in Iceland rather than in larger communities, because Iceland is such a small community that local politicians are more accessible than they would be in one of the larger countries of Europe or the world.

5. Publishing the annotated database

In recent years, Ingason's Language and Technology Lab at the University of Iceland has contributed several Language Resources to online repositories in open access, including both databases and software. Before the end of the EILisCh project, we aim to publish all the extracted data, the manual corrections, as well as the qualitative interviews with a Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY 4.0). It is important to use a permanent and appropriate repository to publish the data and for this we will use the CLARIN system, as we have done for many past projects.

6. Summary

In this paper, we have described the data collection methods of the EILisCh project, a big data digital humanities project that along with its quantitative side, also has a qualitative dimension. We follow, in our opinion, good practices in the collection and distribution of the data, and the fact that all of these will be made publicly available means that subsequent projects on related topics will be able to build on our output.

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